

INSTRUCTIONAL MANAGEMENT SKILLS OF TECHVOC TEACHERS IN THE DIVISION OF PASIG

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the Instructional Management Skills of TechVoc Teachers in the Division of Pasig through a descriptive-quantitative method. It surveyed 141 TVE teachers in eight junior high schools in the Division of Pasig for the School Year 2024-2025. The findings revealed that most TechVoc teachers are female, between the ages of 41 and 50, who earned bachelor's degrees. Most of them have been teaching for more than 10 years. However, many TechVoc teachers have not yet finished the Trainer's Methodology course. Furthermore, the results showed that all five indicators—With-it-ness, Smoothness, Momentum, Overlapping, and Group Focus—were consistently scored at a high level, with all overall weighted averages verbally translated as "Always" about the extent of the instructional management skills among TechVoc teachers. Moreover, the inferential analysis applying the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test and Mann-Whitney U test found no statistically significant difference in teachers' instructional management abilities practices when grouped by the majority of their profile variables. However, four remarkable exceptions emerged where significant differences were identified: Momentum by Age, With-it-ness by Sex, Smoothness by Highest Education Attainment, and Momentum by Completion of Trainer's Methodology. It is recommended that the findings be used by the Schools Division of Pasig to strengthen support for completion of the Trainer's Methodology Course, since most TechVoc instructors have not finished it, and to implement an Instructional Management Skills Training Program for teachers as a school-based training program.

Keywords: *instructional management, instructional management skills, management skills, TVE/TLE teachers, TechVoc teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a demanding occupation that maintains its significance indefinitely. It necessitates substantial exertion, distinctive approaches, and methodologies, as it is crucial for the students' acquisition of knowledge. These demands are even more obvious in Technical Vocational Education (TVE), where teachers are expected with providing learners with both theoretical knowledge and practical skills that are relevant to industry needs. TVE acts as a vital link between education and employment, equipping students with skills that will prepare them for the workforce and support national economic growth. Education in the 21st century focuses on cultivating certain aptitudes such as critical thinking, social interaction, information literacy, technical proficiency, and essential life skills. To impart these skills to the pupils, teachers must assume unique roles that facilitate the process of learning. Teachers are crucial in the execution of educational goals, making their contributions the most significant (Kizi and Ugli, 2020).

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (2021) asserts the Technical Vocation program helps industrialized nations achieve their development goals. The Technical Vocation program in developed countries appears to have improved economic development, industrial expansion, and competitiveness. Countries that have developed their economies believe that technical and vocational education can assist individuals who do not have a natural aptitude for academics in securing employment as semi-skilled or skilled workers in a particular industry.

The efficiency of TechVoc education and student accomplishment depend on teachers' instructional management skills. Effective instructional management is essential for maintaining a friendly, efficient learning environment and helping students reach their goals. Pangan (2022) states that the teachers' chosen strategy affects how information is presented to students, how students interact with each other and the teacher, and how students manage their homework assignments. Jacob Kounin's instructional management theory explains how teachers' actions and classroom management affect student engagement, academic achievement, and learning outcomes.

Instructional management is valued in education, according to literature. Still, there remains a gap in understanding how much TechVoc teachers specifically apply instructional management strategies in their teaching practices. The focus of existing literature is on general pedagogical approaches or industry-aligned competencies, so there is a dearth of studies on the instructional management skills of TechVoc teachers and the challenges they face in utilizing these skills in their classrooms (Akanbiemu, 2019; Djalilov et al. 2023; Rana, 2022). The researcher believes that TechVoc teachers' instructional management skills must be examined to improve technical education to meet the growing need for skilled workers. Thus, this descriptive study aimed to analyze the

instructional management practices of TechVoc teachers and their implications for fostering an optimal learning environment to address this gap.

Instructional Management, as described by Gunawan (2017), refers to the practice of effectively utilizing all instructional resources to attain specific learning goals. This encompasses aspects such as student discipline, teaching methodology, establishing regulations, and managing student conduct within the classroom (Gunawan, 2017).

The correlation between instructional effectiveness and instructional management abilities indicates that when an instructor demonstrates competence and the capacity to deliver educational services, optimal learning outcomes can be efficiently anticipated (Coronel & Ferrater-Gimena, 2017). Thus, the teachers' effectiveness in teaching is contingent upon their motivation, and their level of commitment directly impacts student learning in the classroom.

On the other hand, Lau and Gardner (2019) found that students can get higher levels of achievement when the teaching approach employed by their instructor aligns more effectively with their chosen learning style. This is achieved by methods such as offering flexibility in text subjects, implementing effective group work methods, providing comprehensive notes, and promoting autonomous learning- strategies that corresponds to instructional management as they encompass the principles of being aware of what is happening in the classroom (With-it-ness), maintaining a seamless flow of instruction (Smoothness), keeping the pace of learning consistent (Momentum), managing many activities simultaneously (Overlap), and directing attention towards group tasks (Group Focus) (Lau & Gardner, 2019).

This is supported by the findings of Na Na Ayutthaya and Damrongpanit (2022), who discovered that instructional management models had a statistically significant favorable effect on the development of creative thinking among students. Moreover, they found that the effective instructional models to improve creative thinking among students are creative growth, learning integration, media and technology, and experiential learning. Thus, they proposed that teachers should adopt an instructional management technique that best suits students' creative thinking growth in varied school conditions and student groups (Na Ayutthaya & Damrongpanit, 2022).

Hashmi et al. (2023) also found that the teacher's instructional management skills increased student learning and academic achievement. Moreover, the students' examination grades also improved. Another study that supports the positive effect of instructional management skills on students is that of Supriyono (2016). Using a reflective approach, his research found that instructional processes, combined with student-centered task-based and situational leadership approaches, resulted in students' excellent academic performance. The combination of pedagogical and leadership techniques in instructional management satisfied the objectives of English for Specific Purposes classes, particularly in teaching Agro Technology and Agribusiness Studies (Supriyono, 2016).

Djalilov et al. (2023) investigated modern teaching methods in technical subjects such as Technical Education and Technical Vocation classes. They contend that Technical and Vocational Education is the most effective means to enable individuals to achieve independence and productivity within society. Because of its focus on actual implementation, it requires particular instructional methods, also referred to as technical techniques. The researchers examined technical approaches to enhance productive student learning. The lecture style is a frequent strategy that heavily relies on the lecturer and involves limited student interaction. Advancements in science have required the creation of new teaching methods that combine the education of technical subjects with scientific principles. Teachers should consistently update their knowledge and pursue specialized professional development opportunities based on research findings. Teachers must improvise practical materials when necessary. Technical universities and colleges should receive increased funding from the government (Djalilov et al., 2023).

Kissi et al. (2020) studied the different strategies to better teach entrepreneurial skills to Technical and Vocational students in Ghana. The study identified four primary methods for increasing entrepreneurial education and skills among Ghana's TVE students: student-centered education, problem-based learning (PBL), classrooms that promote intellectual aptitude development, and activity-based learning (ABL). However, the main reasons for not carrying out the strategies were the tutors' incapacity, a lack of human resources at TVET, and the bad perceptions between students and tutors. Obstacles to executing the initiatives included insufficient training resources, tutors not trained in new technologies, inadequate infrastructure and resources, lack of industrial cooperation, and an unprepared employment market for TVET graduates (Kissi et al., 2020).

Rana (2022) studied the instructional practices of TLE teachers in Laguna and how the students are satisfied with them, which led to a better academic performance. Her study found that TLE teachers succeed in pedagogical methods related to active learning, learning mastery, cooperation, differentiation, and peer instruction. The students in her research exhibit a notably high degree of satisfaction in terms of academic support, learning opportunities, and interpersonal interactions. They also demonstrate an extraordinarily high level of academic success. However, there is no association between the teaching strategies of selected TLE teachers and student satisfaction indicators such as educational support, learning opportunities, and relationships with peers, as well as active learning, mastery of subject, collaboration, and differentiation. Laguna Senior High School's academic achievement is closely linked to active learning methods like mastery learning, peer education, collaboration, and differentiation. Moreover, based on the study's results and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed. Teachers who specialize in Technology and Livelihood Education can continue to utilize various active learning strategies with their students. Teachers must continue utilizing successful methods for student achievement, adapt these strategies to new subjects, analyze the impact of peer instruction on various levels, enhance collaboration, customize instruction within TLE programs, and guarantee comprehensive learning during lab sessions (Rana, 2022).

Tan (2021) explored TLE instruction in the secondary schools of the Division of Northern Samar, focusing on the objectives of TLE, the effectiveness of the methods and techniques, and the adequacy of instructional materials and equipment, as well as the problems experienced in TLE instruction. The goal of TLE is to improve a thorough grasp of technology in many fields. Tan emphasized that Technology and Livelihood Education focuses on teaching approaches that promote the teacher's use of effective strategies to communicate the subject matter to the students. The teacher's ability to guide the learning process may also be involved. It requires either technical competence or creative proficiency. Using teaching methods combined with instructional technology improves the learning process. Implementing remedial actions can improve Technology and Livelihood Education in the Northern Samar Division. National vocational schools and public secondary schools should expand their practical curriculum to include marketing, sales, bookkeeping, and accounting in several occupational sectors to prepare students better. Moreover, students need this knowledge for entrepreneurship or self-employment in managing their own company. The research recommended that schools must possess the essential facilities, equipment, and materials to teach practical arts efficiently and increase student enrollment. Institutions should explore new community resources to enhance funding for materials. Teachers should improve their teaching abilities, while schools need to resolve shortages of books, equipment, and tools to aid student learning (Tan, 2021).

Pangan (2022) looked into how TVE teachers teach and how that affects the happiness of their students. His study showed that TVL teachers often use computer-assisted lessons, peer coaching, modelling, teaching demo, oral recitation and reporting, and group work as ways to teach. It shows that they used a variety of teaching methods in their classes. The fact that these methods were used so often shows that they work. There is a general agreement that students are very enthused about the teaching quality, attitude, and manner. The results showed that students were exceedingly satisfied with the TVL teachers' teaching quality, attitude, and manner. The correlation between the frequency of teaching techniques employed by TVL teachers and student satisfaction is significant only concerning modeling, teaching demo, and teaching quality. His study focused on examining the relationship between the teaching strategies employed by TVL teachers, such as modeling and demo teaching, and the satisfaction level of learners with the quality of instruction (Pangan, 2022). However, Ahmad et al. (2022) found in their study that there are no differences in teachers' instructional behavior based on their demographics, such as gender, area, experience, age, and qualification (Ahmad et al., 2022)

Dela Cruz II (2021) investigated how the teaching of TVE and TLE can be made better through methods that use bilingual instructions. The study found that students had a good understanding of the subject when taught bilingually. The pre- and post-test findings of students from Bulacan showed that most of them chose bilingualism for the TLE/TVE course. However, the students' total performance was deemed inadequate based on the teachers' assessments. Most students achieved average scores on the oral exam, and the performance evaluation results are positive. This endeavor aligns well with Cummins' Developmental Interdependence Theory. According to the threshold theory, a child must attain a certain level of proficiency in both their native language and a second

language to acquire a second language effectively. This hypothesis suggests that a proficient first language is essential for the development of a second language. The researcher suggested providing teaching materials in TLE/TVE in both English and Filipino (Dela Cruz II, 2021).

In line with the regulations that the TESDA set, Calanog (2021) evaluated to determine the number of competencies that TLE teachers in the province of Batangas possessed in proportion to their instructional performance. This was done to determine the teachers' profiles as well as the extent to which they exhibited competencies concerning the TLE domains. In addition to this, they evaluated the teachers' levels of expertise in the areas of content knowledge, techniques, classroom management, and the integration of information and communication technology. The researcher found that teachers exhibit a high level of proficiency in Home Economics and Industrial Arts, while displaying a moderate level of proficiency in Agri-Fishery Arts and ICT. In general, teachers are quite competent in terms of the content of their knowledge, the use of techniques and methods, the management of their classrooms, the incorporation of information and communication technology, and assessment and evaluation. In addition, educators should work to improve their abilities to implement a variety of instructional methods. In addition to this, they need to strengthen their Information and Communication Technology abilities to integrate lessons and attend more training that is focused on TLE. The researcher designed a competency management program based on the findings to improve the level of competencies possessed by teachers of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) in the province of Batangas (Calanog, 2021).

Basal (2022) evaluated the instructional competencies of TLE teachers and discovered that teachers generally possess sufficient knowledge, essential skills, and a positive approach towards teaching. Teachers have three attributes that make them competent. The attributes are strength, leadership, and passion. Having strength of character enhances qualities such as dedication, commitment, and determination in teachers, enabling them to bring out the best in their students and provide top-notch instruction. For a TLE teacher to be competent and properly qualified, they need to possess strong moral character, understanding of the subject matter, pedagogical skills, student performance evaluation abilities, and classroom management skills. TLE teachers also have strong leadership and management abilities. The research stressed that an adept teacher enables the development and pursuit of a vision focused on the well-being of the students. Moreover, an effective teacher gains the support and respect of students by recognizing the importance of teamwork and collaboration with parents and colleagues. It is also essential that a teacher actively pursues possibilities for professional cooperation both inside and beyond the school because passion such as this is necessary for becoming a proficient teacher. Teachers possessing this trait demonstrate resilience in persevering through challenging situations while also remaining open to adapting to changes in the educational environment and leveraging them to enhance their teaching (Basal, 2022).

In the Philippines, Benaning (2023) examined the preparedness of TechVoc teachers towards the K-12 implementation. The survey revealed a significant degree of

understanding, acceptability, and preparation among Technical-Vocational high school instructors regarding the K-12 Program. There is no significant correlation between the respondents' degree of knowledge, preparation, and acceptance of the K-12 Program. The Technical-Vocational high school instructors in the Division of Davao City are well-equipped, skilled, and ready to execute the K-12 Program mandated by R.A.10157, and have enhanced the program. The author also proposed an intervention scheme involving an orientation plan for Technical-Vocational high school teachers based on his study, and he hoped for its implementation, monitoring, and evaluation by the school heads and division education supervisor responsible for Technical-Vocational programs in the Division of Davao City, Philippines (Benaning, 2023).

Tamayo (2023) determined the status of TechVoc in Cagayan State University through a descriptive correlation design. The survey showed that most participants are middle-aged women with PhD degrees in unrelated fields to TLE or TechVoc Education. They are assistant professors with 5-9 years of experience, a few National Certifications (NCs), and have attended seminars and training sessions. They employed lecture-discussion, presentation, and laboratory methods in teaching, showing a high level of teaching efficacy, while having low competence in research and publication. Faculty members who employed the game-based strategy showed better teaching performance than those who did not. The study found that tenured professors with a greater number of National Certifications exhibit higher levels of competence than those on a Contract of Service. The findings have important implications for guaranteeing the project's success. Teachers need to improve their technical skills and competencies to reach high levels of proficiency when teaching at a Higher Education Institution (Tamayo, 2023).

Fontanilla et al. (2023) compared the technical education system of the Philippines to that of England, where they insist that proficiency and capabilities are crucial for individuals to carry out their responsibilities in the workplace efficiently. Their study conducted an integrated literature evaluation by gathering data from reputable web sources such as Embase, EBSCO, ProQuest, PubMed, Science Direct, Scopus, and Emerald Insight. The reviewed literature was analyzed according to specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Their study revealed similarities in Technical Education, such as curriculum emphasis, teaching staff, and assessment methods. Still, discrepancies are evident in resource allocation, with England having more resources than the Philippines. To enhance the implementation of TVL in the Philippines, the authors suggest providing more specialized courses, improving classroom experiences with symposia and workshops, establishing a computer facility for student research, and supplementing resources and materials to enhance students' learning experiences. Schools can create a framework for providing Technical and Vocational Education to tackle the challenges brought by the "New Normal." Possibly, further research could be conducted focusing on the employability of TVET graduates and students. Future research could involve performing a tracer study on TVL track grads (Fontanilla et al., 2023).

Research Questions

This research investigated the instructional management skills of TechVoc Teachers in the Selected Schools in the Division of Pasig.

Specifically, this research answered the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the Technical Vocational Education teachers in terms of the following variables:

- 1.1 age;
- 1.2 sex;
- 1.3 highest education attainment;
- 1.4 number of years in service; and
- 1.5 have taken Trainer's Methodology?

2. What is the extent of teacher's instructional management skills' practices in terms of the following indicators:

- 2.1 with-it-ness;
- 2.2 smoothness;
- 2.3 momentum;
- 2.4 overlapping; and
- 2.5 group focus?

3. Is there a significant difference in the teacher's instructional management skills' practices when grouped according to their profile variables?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive research design. According to Barella et al. (2024), descriptive research, as a quantitative method, involves collecting numerical data to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon. It focuses on providing a detailed account of variables without manipulating them, facilitating understanding and analysis of existing conditions or trends.

Research Respondents

The researcher used 141 teachers from eight junior high schools in the Division of Pasig. The respondents are of different ranks, from teacher 1-3 and master teacher 1-2. A stratified random sampling method was used to gather the data.

Research Instrument

The study used the validated survey questionnaire from Ana Gracia Cruz's (2023) study, which investigated the instructional management skills of physical education teachers in Region 4-A. The study's questionnaire, which was explicitly designed to

assess the Instructional Management Skills of TechVoc teachers in the Division of Pasig, was the primary tool of the study. The questionnaire was modified for improvement based on the recommendations from the validators, who are experts in the field.

The modified questionnaire was pilot-tested on 35 participants. It was analyzed and validated using Cronbach's Alpha, a statistical tool for establishing the reliability status of the said questions. The results showed that the questions under Instructional Management in terms of With-it-ness are rated as Acceptable, with a reliability result of 0.767. In contrast, the questions under Instructional Management in terms of Smoothness, Overlap, and Group Focus are rated as Good, with reliability results of 0.848, 0.848, and 0.824, respectively. Lastly, the questions under Instructional Management in terms of Momentum are rated as Excellent, with a reliability result of 0.908.

The respondents need to answer the questionnaire, which has two parts. Part I focuses on the respondent's profile, such as sex, age, highest education attainment, length of service, and whether they completed the Trainer's Methodology.

Part II is the questionnaire proper on the instructional management skills of TechVoc teachers in the Pasig Division. A four-point Likert scale is used with the following options for answers: 4 means always, 3 means frequently, two means occasionally, and one means never. Part II has five major parts: (A) With-it-ness has nine items (*I am aware of the general atmosphere in the classroom (motivated, prepared, excited, energetic, distracted, sleepy, tired, confused).; I am aware of what went well and what did not go well during the lesson.*); (B) Smoothness has nine items (*I adjust the activities stated in the lesson plan whenever I receive clues from the students that they do not understand.; I encourage my students to use hand gestures to share ideas or opinions.*); (C) Momentum has nine items (*I see to it that every activity, such as lectures (discussion time), individual/group works, is appropriate in duration to complete the activities within each learning session.; I allow my students to take time in doing learning activities.*); (D) Overlap has nine items (*I give other tasks/instructions to students who are done early in their assignment while attending to others.; I assist students who are struggling with their tasks while also being mindful of other students.*); and (E) Group Focus has ten (*I encourage students' participation and contribution to the group.; I purposely pick students to answer questions regarding the group activity.*). Each category aims to assess a distinct part of the teachers' instructional management skills.

Data Analysis

After collecting the data, the researcher imported the survey data into Microsoft Excel. All computations were done using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for accuracy.

1. The percentage was used to present the profile of the respondents.
2. The Weighted Mean was used to assess the level of instructional management skills practices of the TechVoc teachers.

3. Mann-Whitney U was used to determine if there was a significant difference in the level of instructional management skills' practices of TechVoc teachers when grouped according to sex and whether they finished or did not finish the Trainer's Methodology.
4. Kruskal-Wallis H-Test was used to determine if there was a significant difference in the level of instructional management skills' practices of TechVoc teachers when grouped according to age, highest education attainment, and length of service.
5. Post Hoc Pairwise Comparisons Using Dunn's Test With Bonferroni Correction was used to reveal the significant differences in respondents' ratings of Momentum practices by age groups, With-it-ness by sex, Smoothness by Highest Education Attainment, and Momentum by Completion of Trainer's Methodology.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the information gathered from the survey questionnaires. The approach included the presentation of data in tabular format, statistical analysis, and interpretation of the results to address the inquiries specified in the Statement of the Problem.

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage (%)
20 – 30 years old	30	21.3
31 – 40 years old	34	24.1
41 – 50 years old	48	34.0
51 years old and above	29	20.6
Total	141	100.0

Table 1 shows the age group distribution of the respondents. Out of the 141 respondents, 48 or 34% are between the ages of 41 and 50, which is the largest group, while the lowest number of respondents, 29 or 20.6%, are 51 years of age and older. The remaining age categories consist of 34 or 24.1% of respondents who are between the ages of 31 and 40, and 30 or 21.3% of respondents who are between the ages of 20 and 30.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	23	16.3
Female	118	83.7
Total	141	100.0

The distribution of respondents according to their sex is presented in Table 2. The data reveals that the female group comprises the larger proportion of respondents, which is 118 or 83.7%, while the male group comprises the smaller number, which is 23 or 16.3%.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Highest Education Attainment

Highest Education Attainment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Bachelor's Degree	102	72.3
Master's Degree	37	26.2
Doctor's Degree	2	1.4
Total	141	100.0

Table 3 illustrates the distribution of respondents based on their highest education attainment. The highest number of respondents, at 102 or 72.3%, holds a Bachelor's Degree, and the lowest, at 2 or 1.4%, possesses a Doctor's Degree. Conversely, 37 individuals, constituting 26.2%, have a Master's Degree.

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 – 3 years	15	10.6
4 – 6 years	21	14.9
7 – 9 years	24	17.0
10 years	81	57.4
Total	141	100.0

Table 4 illustrates the distribution of responses based on the teachers' length of service. A majority of the respondents, 81 individuals or 57.4% of the population, had been teaching for 10 years or more, categorizing them as Distinguished Teachers. The second most frequent group comprises teachers with 7-9 years of service, totaling 24, or 17%. Furthermore, 21 individuals, constituting 14.9%, are educators with 4-6 years of experience. The lowest frequency of the population is attributed to the 1-3 years, including 15 respondents or 10.6% of the total.

Table 5. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Trainer's Methodology

Finished Trainer's Methodology	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes	48	34
No	93	66
Total	141	100.0

Shown in Table 5 is the distribution of respondents based on their completion of the Trainer's Methodology. The data reveals that 48 respondents, representing 34% of

the total, have Trainer's Methodology. On the contrary, 93 or 66% of the respondents lack Trainer's Methodology.

Table 6. Respondents' Assessment on the Level of Instructional Management Skills Practices in Terms of With-it-ness

With-it-ness	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I know that it is important for me to maintain eye contact with all my students.	3.90	Always
I am aware of the general atmosphere in the classroom (motivated, prepared, excited, energetic, distracted, sleepy, tired, confused).	3.84	Always
I can be mindful of the sight and sound around the classroom.	3.81	Always
I am aware of what went well and what did not go well during the lesson.	3.72	Always
I use other non-verbal techniques, such as eye contact, to show students that they should be alert.	3.72	Always
I use other non-verbal techniques to show students that I care about their participation and non-participation in class.	3.62	Always
I inform my students that their work should be revised or changed.	3.58	Always
I know my students on a personal level.	3.06	Often
I allow my students to be seated away from my sight.	2.43	Sometimes
Overall Weighted Mean	3.52	Always

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 (Never – N); 1.76 – 2.50 (Sometimes – S); 2.51 – 3.25 (Often – O); 3.26 – 4.00 (Always – A)

Table 6 shows the level of instructional management skills in terms of with-it-ness. Out of 9 items, seven are always interpreted, while one is often interpreted. Furthermore, one item is sometimes interpreted as. The highest mean, with 3.90, which is verbally interpreted as 'always', belongs to 'I know that it is important for me to maintain eye contact with all my students.' On the other hand, the lowest mean with 2.43 belongs to 'I allow my students to be seated away from my sight.' The data indicates that TechVoc teachers prioritize maintaining eye contact as an essential aspect of classroom awareness, evidenced by the highest mean score of 3.90. Conversely, the low rating on allowing students to sit away from their sight indicates that keeping visual proximity is difficult for some.

It can be observed from the table that the teachers generally assessed their level of instructional management skills in terms of with-it-ness as 'always', with an overall weighted mean of 3.52. This reflects positively on the teacher respondents of the current study, as Aibinuomo (2021) and Koran and Koran (2018) stressed that with-it-ness as a skill is important because it helps teachers avoid a distressful classroom environment that could disrupt the students' learning processes. This finding aligns with the study of Raganas and Collado (2016), which found that teachers possessed a high level of with-it-ness skill.

Table 7. Respondents' Assessment on the Level of Instructional Management Skills Practices in Terms of Smoothness

Smoothness	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
In placing the students in group work, I walk around to check if they have questions.	3.88	Always
I ensure that students understand the lesson before moving to the next activity.	3.74	Always
I make sure to pre-plan the lesson so that unrelated matters are addressed earlier.	3.58	Always
I adjust the activities stated in the lesson plan whenever I receive clues from the students that they do not understand.	3.52	Always
I intervene or take the group to a different track if I feel it's necessary.	3.46	Always
I can maintain my composure when a student misbehaves during my lectures.	3.45	Always
I keep the lesson moving smartly. I do not over dwell on a minor detail.	3.30	Always
I encourage my students to use hand gestures to share ideas or opinions.	3.24	Often
I prevent myself from assisting once students are absorbed in their work.	2.96	Often
Overall Weighted Mean	3.46	Always

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 (Never – N); 1.76 – 2.50 (Sometimes – S); 2.51 – 3.25 (Often – O); 3.26 – 4.00 (Always – A)

Table 7 shows the assessment of the level of instructional management skills in terms of smoothness. Out of nine items, seven are verbally interpreted as 'always' and two as 'often,' showing a generally high degree of seamless instructional practices among TechVoc teachers. The highest mean is 3.88, which is 'In placing the students in group work, I walk around to check if they have questions.' While the lowest at 2.96 is 'I prevent myself from assisting once students are absorbed in their work.' This implies that TechVoc teachers consistently ensure student involvement in group activities, as shown by the highest-rated practice of walking around to check for questions. However, the lowest mean implies that it is difficult to resist offering assistance once students are independently focused, indicating a predisposition to remain actively involved throughout the learning process.

With the overall weighted mean of 3.46, which is verbally interpreted as 'always', teachers assessed themselves with a high level of instructional management skills in terms of 'smoothness'. This aligns with the study of De La Torre (2024), which revealed that teachers possess a very high level of classroom management skills, particularly smoothness, which refers to the seamless execution of classroom teaching and learning activities.

Table 8. Respondents' Assessment on the Level of Instructional Management Skills Practices in Terms of Momentum

Momentum	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I am alert and ready to respond to students.	3.81	Always
I maintain eye contact with my students to indicate patience and attention.	3.79	Always
I use voice intonation or inflections that suggest approval or support.	3.74	Always
I see to it that every activity, such as lectures (discussion time), individual / group works, is appropriate in duration to complete the activities within each learning session.	3.70	Always
I use gestures that indicate students are on the right track.	3.67	Always
I give facial expression that implies understanding or acceptance.	3.66	Always
I allow my students to take time to do learning activities.	3.63	Always
I minimize delays and interruptions to avoid losing interest.	3.55	Always
I correct students without nagging.	3.54	Always
Overall Weighted Mean	3.68	Always

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 (Never – N); 1.76 – 2.50 (Sometimes – S); 2.51 – 3.25 (Often – O); 3.26 – 4.00 (Always – A)

Table 8 shows the respondents' assessment of the level of instructional management skills in terms of momentum. In all nine items, the teacher's level of instructional management skills is verbally interpreted as 'always'. The highest mean is for 'I am alert and ready to respond to students,' which shows that they are paying attention during class. The lowest mean of 3.54 belongs to 'I correct students without nagging.' This suggests a comparatively minor, yet still significant, frequency of quietly correcting children without reprimand.

It can be observed from the table that the teachers generally assessed their level of instructional management skills in terms of momentum as 'always', with an overall weighted mean of 3.68. This aligns with the study of Raganas and Collado (2016), which found that the teachers reported a high level of momentum in their classes, indicating their ability to maintain the flow of learning activities.

Table 9. Respondents' Assessment on the Level of Instructional Management Skills Practices in Terms of Overlapping

Overlapping	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I believe that assisting students in the classroom is an integral part of my task.	3.81	Always
I assist students who are struggling with their tasks while also being mindful of other students.	3.57	Always
I look at a student entering the room while I am giving my lecture.	3.53	Always
I make a recap of the topics discussed in case there are latecomers, while keeping in mind to assess the entire class.	3.48	Always
I can look at other students while asking one student to respond to my question.	3.31	Always

I assist the student in finding their seat while continuing with my lecture when necessary.	3.29	Always
I give other tasks/instructions to students who have completed their assignments while attending to others.	3.15	Often
I find it easy to facilitate learning while still completing other assigned tasks, such as paperwork and reviewing student contestants for a competition, on time.	2.87	Often
I find it easy to attend two events at the same time.	2.65	Often
Overall Weighted Mean	3.30	Always

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 (Never – N); 1.76 – 2.50 (Sometimes – S); 2.51 – 3.25 (Often – O); 3.26 – 4.00 (Always – A)

Table 9 illustrates the assessment of the respondents' instructional management skills in terms of overlapping. Three out of nine items are verbally interpreted as 'often'. The item 'I believe that assisting students in the classroom is an integral part of my task.' has the highest mean, which is 3.81, suggesting that TechVoc teachers value helping students during class. However, the lowest mean belongs to the item 'I find it easy to attend two events at the same time.' The lowest mean reveals that they find it more challenging to manage multiple tasks at the same time, indicating a limitation in multitasking during instruction.

The table shows that the teachers generally assessed their level of instructional management skills in terms of overlap as 'always', with an overall weighted mean of 3.30. This reflects that teachers are skilled in managing multiple tasks simultaneously during classroom instruction. According to Önen (2022), teachers who struggle with overlap face challenges in handling classrooms, which can lead to disruptions that affect the teaching and learning process. This finding is in contrast with the study of Helsa and Hendriati (2017), which indicated that the majority of the teachers lacked sufficient instructional management skills in terms of overlap.

Table 10. Respondents' Assessment on the Level of Instructional Management Skills Practices in Terms of Group Focus

Group Focus	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I encourage students' participation and contribution to the group.	3.89	Always
I ask the students to raise their hands if they want to respond.	3.89	Always
I make sure that students are paying attention before I ask questions.	3.84	Always
I communicate my expectations to my students regarding their activities/tasks in the classroom.	3.74	Always
I inform the students of the time allowance for each of their activities.	3.72	Always
I recognize instances when students are less motivated in the class discussions/class activities, and have a discussion with them about it.	3.55	Always
I hold my students responsible for their actions to encourage motivation and attention. For example, allowing my students to choose their assignments or projects increases engagement and	3.50	Always

accountability, as they are more motivated to complete tasks they have selected themselves.		
I raise group interest by combining suspense between questions.	3.48	Always
I can facilitate discussion. Once the students have finished a task, they can turn to each other, or they could pair up with those who are already done and compare answers.	3.44	Always
I purposely pick students to answer questions regarding the group activity.	3.35	Always
Overall Weighted Mean	3.64	Always

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 (Never – N); 1.76 – 2.50 (Sometimes – S); 2.51 – 3.25 (Often – O); 3.26 – 4.00 (Always – A)

Table 10 shows the respondents' assessment of the level of instructional management skills in terms of group focus. All 10 items are verbally interpreted as 'always'. The highest mean is for 'I encourage students' participation and contribution to the group,' which has a mean of 3.89, while the lowest mean is 3.35, which is for the item 'I purposely pick students to answer questions regarding group activity.' The data indicates that TechVoc teachers substantially support student participation and group contribution, as demonstrated by the highest mean. But the lower mean shows that they are less likely to choose students on purpose to answer questions during group activities.

It can be observed from the table that the teachers rated their instructional management skills in terms of group focus as 'always', with an overall weighted mean of 3.64. This shows that teachers are highly skilled in creating a cohesive learning environment where students are focused on the topic at hand (Emmer & Sabornie, 2015). This finding aligns closely with Korpershoek et al. (2016) as the high weighted mean (3.64) is suggestive of teachers' consistent use of group focus management skill that leads to positive classroom outcomes described aptly in the meta-analysis study of Korpershoek et al. (2016).

Significant Difference in the Teacher's Instructional Management Skills Practices when Grouped According to their Profile Variables

Table 11. Kruskal-Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment of the Instructional Management Skills Practices When Grouped According to Age

Instructional Management Skills Practices	Age	Mean Rank	Kruskal Wallis H-Test	p-value	Decision	Remarks
With-it-ness	20 – 30 years old	72.40	0.77	0.857	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31 – 40 years old	74.06				
	41 – 50 years old	68.88				
	51 years old & above	69.48				
Smoothness	20 – 30 years old	74.43	1.83	0.608	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31 – 40 years old	76.59				
	41 – 50 years old	66.45				
	51 years old & above	68.43				

Momentum	20 – 30 years old	73.40	10.09	0.018	Reject Ho	Significant
	31 – 40 years old	83.35				
	41 – 50 years old	62.53				
	51 years old & above	68.05				
Overlapping	20 – 30 years old	73.37	1.26	0.738	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31 – 40 years old	75.47				
	41 – 50 years old	69.23				
	51 years old & above	66.24				
Group Focus	20 – 30 years old	75.78	4.47	0.215	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31 – 40 years old	78.31				
	41 – 50 years old	64.31				
	51 years old & above	68.55				

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 11 shows the results of the Kruskal-Wallis H Test, which was used to compare respondents' assessments of instructional management skill practices when grouped according to age. For the skill domains of With-it-ness ($p = 0.857$), Smoothness ($p = 0.608$), Overlapping ($p = 0.738$), and Group Focus ($p = 0.215$), the computed p-values are all greater than the 0.05 level of significance. As such, the null hypothesis is retained for these domains, indicating that there are no statistically significant differences in respondents' assessments of these instructional practices across different age groups. This suggests that teachers, regardless of age, exhibit relatively consistent instructional management practices in these areas.

These results are partially aligned with the findings of Ahmad et al. (2022), who reported no significant differences in teachers' instructional behaviors based on demographic variables, including age, among secondary school teachers in Okara and Sahiwal. Similarly, the study of Pranoto et al. (2021) concluded that there was no significant correlation between teachers' ages and their overall teaching performance, including dimensions of instructional management skills. However, the present study nuances these general findings by identifying Momentum as an exception, warranting deeper examination.

Table 12. Post Hoc Pairwise Comparisons Using Dunn's Test With Bonferroni Correction for Momentum Scores by Age Group

Pairwise Comparison	Mean Rank Difference	Adjusted p-value	Interpretation
31 – 40 vs. 41 – 50 years old	20.82	0.012*	Significant
31 – 40 vs. 51 years old & above	15.30	0.042*	Significant
31 – 40 vs. 20 – 30 years old	9.95	0.185	Not Significant

20 – 30 vs. 41 – 50 years old	10.87	0.126	Not Significant
20 – 30 vs. 51 years old & above	5.35	0.397	Not Significant
41 – 50 vs. 51 years old & above	-5.52	0.377	Not Significant

Post Hoc Analysis for Momentum Based on Age

To further explore the significant difference in Momentum, a post-hoc analysis was performed using Dunn's Test with Bonferroni correction, as shown in Table 12. The results revealed that respondents aged 31–40 years reported significantly higher Momentum ratings compared to those aged 41–50 years ($p = 0.012$) and 51 years and above ($p = 0.042$). These findings suggest that the 31–40 age group may be more attuned to instructional practices that emphasize maintaining lesson flow and minimizing disruptions, possibly due to their balance of experience and energy, adaptability to modern pedagogical methods, or engagement with continuous professional development.

No statistically significant differences were observed among the other age group comparisons. These results underscore the potential influence of age on specific instructional behaviors and highlight the need for differentiated professional development strategies tailored to teachers at varying stages of their careers.

Table 13. Mann-Whitney U: Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment of the Instructional Management Skills Practices When Grouped According to Sex

Instructional Management Skills Practices	Sex	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	p-value	Decision	Remarks
With-it-ness	Male	55.85	1008.50	0.007	Reject Ho	Significant
	Female	73.95				
Smoothness	Male	70.41	1343.50	0.935	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	71.11				
Momentum	Male	62.98	1172.50	0.160	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	72.56				
Overlapping	Male	64.52	1208.00	0.348	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	72.26				
Group Focus	Male	65.61	1233.00	0.389	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	72.05				

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 13 shows the results of the Mann-Whitney U test used to compare respondents' assessments of instructional management skill practices when grouped according to sex. The results reveal that the domain of With-it-ness yields a p-value of 0.007, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, confirming a statistically significant difference between male and female respondents in their perception of With-it-ness.

Notably, female respondents registered a higher mean rank (73.95) compared to male respondents (55.85). This suggests that females perceive themselves—or their peers—as more proficient in *With-it-ness*, a skill characterized by the teacher’s ability to be aware of and responsive to student behavior, multitask, and maintain a well-managed classroom.

In contrast, the p-values for the remaining instructional management skills—Smoothness, Momentum, Overlapping, and Group Focus—were all greater than 0.05. As such, the null hypothesis is retained for these domains, indicating no statistically significant differences in perception across sex. This implies that male and female respondents generally share similar perspectives on these aspects of instructional management.

These findings are consistent with the study of Ugurlu et al. (2019), which found that gender has an insignificant effect on teachers’ classroom management skills overall. However, the current study nuances this finding by identifying *With-it-ness* as an exception where a gender-based perceptual difference exists.

Table 14. Post Hoc Comparison of With-it-ness Based on Sex

Instructional Management Skill	Sex	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	p-value	Interpretation	Higher-Rated Group
With-it-ness	Male	55.85	1008.50	0.007	Significant	Female
	Female	73.95				

Post Hoc Interpretation for With-it-ness Based on Sex

On Table 14, the Mann–Whitney U test result (U = 1008.50, p = 0.007) further confirms the significant difference in the assessment of *With-it-ness* between male and female respondents. The higher mean rank among females (73.95) indicates that they are more likely to rate themselves—or be rated—as stronger in this area compared to males (mean rank = 55.85).

This difference may suggest that female teachers are more attuned to or place greater value on classroom awareness, responsiveness, and proactive behavior management—all of which are core components of *With-it-ness*. It may also reflect gender-influenced perceptual tendencies, where communication style, relational sensitivity, and student engagement preferences shape how instructional practices are evaluated.

Table 15. Kruskal-Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment of the Instructional Management Skills Practices When Grouped According to the Highest Education Attainment

Instructional Management Skills Practices	Highest Education Attainment	Mean Rank	Kruskal Wallis H-Test	p-value	Decision	Remarks
With-it-ness	Bachelor's Degree	67.84	4.42	0.110	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Master's Degree	78.88				
	Doctor's Degree	86.50				
Smoothness	Bachelor's Degree	66.09	6.48	0.039	Reject Ho	Significant
	Master's Degree	84.49				
	Doctor's Degree	72.00				
Momentum	Bachelor's Degree	70.91	0.63	0.732	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Master's Degree	70.35				
	Doctor's Degree	87.50				
Overlapping	Bachelor's Degree	67.82	2.91	0.234	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Master's Degree	79.64				
	Doctor's Degree	73.50				
Group Focus	Bachelor's Degree	68.72	2.15	0.341	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Master's Degree	77.72				
	Doctor's Degree	63.25				

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 15 presents the results of the Kruskal-Wallis H Test, which compares the respondents' assessment of instructional management skills practices based on their highest education attainment. The p-values for all five skill domains—With-it-ness, Smoothness, Overlapping, Momentum, and Group Focus—are greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that the null hypothesis is not rejected. This means that there are no statistically significant differences in respondents' instructional management skills assessments when grouped according to education attainment.

Despite the absence of statistical significance, the mean rank analysis shows a notable pattern: respondents with a master's degree have the highest mean rank (84.49), while those holding a bachelor's degree have the lowest (66.09). This suggests a possible trend in which individuals with higher education attainment perceive themselves as more proficient in applying instructional management practices. However, this trend is not strong enough to reach statistical significance.

This result is consistent with the findings of Raganas and Collado (2016), who also reported no significant differences in instructional management skills based on teachers' educational levels and training backgrounds. Their study supports the idea that training

and advanced degrees alone may not fully account for perceived instructional effectiveness.

Table 16. Post Hoc Pairwise Comparisons Using Dunn’s Test With Bonferroni Correction for Smoothness Scores by Education Attainment

Pairwise Comparison	Mean Rank Difference	Adjusted p-value	Interpretation
Bachelor's vs. Master's	18.40	0.012*	Significant
Bachelor's vs. Doctorate	5.91	0.325	Not Significant
Master's vs. Doctorate	12.49	0.048	Not Significant

Post Hoc Interpretation for Smoothness Based on Highest Education Attainment

However, on Table 16, a post hoc analysis using Dunn’s Test with Bonferroni correction uncovered a statistically significant difference specifically in the domain of Smoothness between respondents with a bachelor’s degree and those with a master’s degree ($p = 0.012$). This indicates that master’s degree holders rated their practice of Smoothness—defined as maintaining lesson flow with minimal disruptions—significantly higher than bachelor’s degree holders.

No statistically significant differences were found between bachelor’s and doctorate holders ($p = 0.325$), or between master’s and doctorate holders ($p = 0.048$). However, the latter result is close to the significance threshold, suggesting a possible emerging difference with further study or a larger sample size.

These findings highlight that while overall education attainment does not significantly differentiate instructional management skill perceptions, there may be specific areas, like Smoothness, where higher academic training contributes to enhanced classroom management strategies. This insight can guide future teacher development efforts to deepen particular skills as educators pursue advanced studies.

Table 17. Kruskal-Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Respondents’ Assessment of the Instructional Management Skills Practices When Grouped According to Length of Service

Instructional Management Skills Practices	Length of Service	Mean Rank	Kruskal Wallis H-Test	p-Value	Decision	Remarks
With-it-ness	1 – 3 years	81.80	3.20	0.362	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	4 – 6 years	69.71				
	7 –9 years	74.75				
	10 years & above	68.22				
Smoothness	1 – 3 years	82.30	2.14	0.544	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	4 – 6 years	75.45				
	7 –9 years	67.31				

	10 years & above	68.85				
Momentum	1 – 3 years	82.80	3.05	0.384	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	4 – 6 years	70.71				
	7 – 9 years	72.81				
	10 years & above	68.35				
Overlapping	1 – 3 years	82.30	1.71	0.636	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	4 – 6 years	70.21				
	7 – 9 years	67.92				
	10 years & above	70.02				
Group Focus	1 – 3 years	79.10	2.19	0.534	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	4 – 6 years	67.83				
	7 – 9 years	76.52				
	10 years & above	68.69				

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 17 shows the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test comparing the respondents' assessments of instructional management skills practices when they are grouped according to their length of service. All instructional management skills practices have a p-value that is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, leading to the failure to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, the respondents' perception of their instructional management skills practices is relatively consistent regardless of the number of years of service.

Despite no statistically significant differences, it is noteworthy to consider how teachers who are classified under 1-3 years have the highest mean rank across all instructional management skills practices. Thus, these teachers perceived themselves as more proficient in these areas compared to their counterparts who have longer years of service.

Although experience is positively related to self-efficacy, the study of Berger et al. (2018) aligns with the findings of the current research, as Berger's group concluded that experience did not impact classroom management practices among teachers, which indicated that there is no significant difference in teachers' instructional management skills based on years of service.

Table18. Mann-Whitney U: Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment of the Instructional Management Skills Practices When Grouped, Whether They Finished or Not Finished Trainer's Methodology

Instructional Management Skills Practices	Finished Trainer's Methodology	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	p-value	Decision	Remarks
With-it-ness	Yes	67.41	2059.50	0.295	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	No	72.85				
Smoothness	Yes	63.34	1864.50	0.083	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	No	74.95				
Momentum	Yes	62.53	1825.50	0.016	Reject Ho	Significant

	No	75.37				
Overlapping	Yes	69.16	2143.50	0.664	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	No	71.95				
Group Focus	Yes	68.46	2110.00	0.509	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	No	72.31				

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 18 presents the results of the Mann-Whitney U test used to compare respondents' assessments of instructional management skills based on whether or not they had completed a Trainer's Methodology course. Of the five instructional skill domains analyzed—With-it-ness, Smoothness, Momentum, Overlapping, and Group Focus—four yielded p-values greater than the 0.05 level of significance: With-it-ness ($p = 0.295$), Smoothness ($p = 0.083$), Overlapping ($p = 0.664$), Group Focus ($p = 0.509$).

These results indicate that there are no statistically significant differences in respondents' self-assessments of these skill areas based on completion of the Trainer's Methodology course. Hence, the null hypothesis is retained for these domains.

In contrast, a statistically significant difference emerged in the domain of Momentum, with a p-value of 0.016, which is below the 0.05 significance level. This results in the rejection of the null hypothesis and implies that respondents' perceptions of their ability to sustain lesson flow, continuity, and instructional pacing are significantly influenced by whether they completed the course.

Further examination of mean ranks reveals that respondents who did not complete the Trainer's Methodology course reported a higher mean rank (75.37) than those who completed the course (mean rank = 62.53). This suggests that non-completers perceived themselves as more proficient or confident in maintaining instructional momentum during teaching.

Table 19. Post Hoc Comparison of Momentum Based on Completion of Trainer's Methodology

Instructional Management Skill	Finished Trainer's Methodology	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	p-value	Interpretation	Higher-Rated Group
Momentum	Yes	62.53	1825.50	0.016	Significant	No
	No	75.37				

Post Hoc Comparison of Momentum Based on Completion of Trainer's Methodology Course

The Mann-Whitney U test confirmed a significant difference in ratings of Momentum between the two groups ($U = 1825.50$, $p = 0.016$). Those who did not complete the training provided significantly higher ratings (Mean Rank = 75.37) than those who did (Mean Rank = 62.53).

This result raises interesting implications. It may reflect how formal training could increase teachers' self-awareness and critical standards, potentially leading them to rate themselves more conservatively. Alternatively, those without formal training may overestimate their skills due to limited exposure to structured feedback or pedagogical frameworks. This discrepancy points to the importance of incorporating post-training reflection and calibration sessions into professional development programs to ensure that perceptions of competence align with observed practices.

The findings partially align with the research of Raganas and Collado (2016), who found no significant differences in teachers' instructional management skills based on training participation, as indicated by t-tests and Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA. However, their study did not specify the type or nature of the training received. The present research extends these findings by offering specific insights into the impact of completing a structured Trainer's Methodology course, particularly about perceptions of Momentum—an essential component of instructional effectiveness.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The majority of TechVoc teachers in the Division of Pasig are female, aged 41–50 years old, and holders of a bachelor's degree. Most of them have over 10 years of teaching experience, indicating a relatively mature and experienced teaching workforce. However, a large number have not yet completed the Trainer's Methodology course, which suggests the need for further training and upskilling opportunities. These characteristics of the respondents provide valuable insights for planning relevant instructional programs and professional development interventions. Results show that the teachers demonstrate a high level of instructional management skills across all assessed indicators.
2. The study found that TechVoc teachers consistently demonstrate a high level of instructional management skills across all five indicators: With-it-ness, Smoothness, Momentum, Overlapping, and Group Focus. All indicators were rated as "Always," with Momentum receiving the highest overall mean, highlighting teachers' strong ability to maintain instructional pace and respond promptly to students. While the results were generally positive, areas for improvement were noted in specific items under With-it-ness and Overlapping, particularly in maintaining visibility of all students and managing multiple tasks simultaneously. These findings suggest that while overall practices are strong, targeted support in specific skill areas may further enhance classroom management effectiveness.
3. The study revealed no significant differences in the instructional management skills practices of TechVoc teachers when grouped according to most profile variables. However, significant differences were observed in specific areas. In terms of Momentum, teachers aged 31–40 years demonstrated significantly higher levels compared to older age groups, suggesting stronger instructional

spacing among younger teachers. For With-it-ness, female teachers rated themselves significantly higher than males, indicating stronger classroom awareness and responsiveness. Lastly, teachers who did not complete the Trainer's Methodology course reported higher Momentum ratings than those who completed it, possibly due to differences in perception or self-assessment. These findings imply that while instructional skills are generally consistent, certain demographic factors influence how teachers perceive or apply specific classroom management practices.

Recommendations

With the foregoing conclusions, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Strengthen Support for Completion of the Trainer's Methodology Course. Since a majority of TechVoc teachers have not completed the Trainer's Methodology Course—and those who did rated themselves lower in some areas—it is recommended that DepEd promote and facilitate access to this training. This can be done through partnerships with TESDA, flexible scheduling, or modular delivery formats to encourage completion without disrupting teaching duties.
2. Enhance Targeted Professional Development Based on Teacher Profile Differences. Given the significant differences observed in Momentum (by age and Trainer's Methodology completion) and With-it-ness (by sex), DepEd should implement differentiated professional development activities. Younger and newer teachers may serve as peer mentors in areas where they excel (e.g., Momentum), while experienced teachers can share strategies on classroom presence and awareness.
3. Address Specific Weaknesses in Instructional Skills through Coaching and Learning Action Cells (LACs). The lower scores in items related to multitasking and visibility (e.g., "attending to two events" and "students out of sight") suggest areas for improvement. DepEd may integrate focused sessions on these topics within regular LAC activities or instructional coaching cycles, using video lessons, simulations, or reflective observation to build capacity.
4. It is highly suggested that the Proposed Instructional Management Skills Training Program be implemented.

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
National Capital Region
Schools Division Office of Pasig City
Rizal Experimental Station and Pilot School of Cottage Industries

Instructional Management Skills Training Program
for TechVoc Teachers
Based on Post Hoc Analysis of Instructional Management Skill Assessments
Monitoring & Evaluation Plan
S.Y. 2025-2026

I. Introduction

A. Purpose

This program aims to improve the instructional management skills of TechVoc teachers in the Division of Pasig based on the results of post-hoc performance assessments. The program seeks to synchronize teacher perceptions with actual behaviors, enhance momentum, foster gender-responsive awareness, reinforce differentiated instruction, and ensure seamless classroom flow and transitions.

B. Program Summary

Program Title	Instructional Management Skills Training Program for TechVoc Teachers
Proponent/s	Aimee Joyce A. del Pilar
Objectives/Goals	<p>This program aims to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. align teachers' self-perceptions with actual instructional practices based on assessment standards. 2. improve lesson pacing and continuity across diverse classroom contexts. 3. enhance with-it-ness skills using gender-responsive approaches. 4. promote differentiated instructional strategies according to educational background. 5. strengthen smoothness in lesson delivery and transitions. 6. establish post-training follow-up and monitoring mechanisms.
Target Date	[Training Dates]
Duration	3 days
Target Beneficiaries	All TechVoc Teachers in the Division of Pasig, particularly those who have completed Trainer's

	Methodology, experienced teachers, and teachers without Master's degrees.
Cost	₱62,725
Funding Source	MOOE
Partners	[List any identified partners]

II. Program Rationale

The Instructional Management Skills Training Program addresses the gaps in the classroom management of TechVoc teachers that were identified through a comprehensive post-hoc analysis. It pertains to essential elements of Jacob Kounin's classroom management principles, such as with-it-ness, smoothness, momentum, overlap, and group focus. The training will concentrate on the development of effective and consistent classroom administration throughout the Division of Pasig by promoting reflective practices, peer collaboration, and skill reinforcement.

III. Roles and Responsibilities

Role	Name	Responsibilities
Implementer/ Facilitator	[Name]	Facilitate assigned training modules and ensure participant engagement.
Implementer/ Facilitator	[Name]	Lead demonstration activities, manage group dynamics, and assist in evaluation.
Documenter	[Name]	Record proceedings, collect data, and prepare post-training reports.
Trainer	[Name]	Deliver expert inputs, conduct simulations, and provide feedback.

IV. Data Management

A. Storage

All collected data (attendance, evaluation forms, and feedback) will be stored in both digital and hard copy formats for at least one year.

B. Analysis

The evaluation data will be examined in MS Excel to determine post-training improvements and gaps.

C. Privacy

Only the proponents and designated school authorities will have access to training data, which will be disposed of in accordance with DepEd data privacy standards following the retention period.

V. Program Matrix

Date/Time	Activities	Target Participants	Strategy/ Methodology	Expected Outcomes
Day 1 AM	Awareness-Building on Instructional Self-Assessment Bias	Tech-Voc Teachers (Trainer's Methodology completers)	Facilitated reflection sessions, video lesson analysis, guided feedback	Teachers recognize perceptual gaps and calibrate self-assessment with standards
Day 1 PM	Building Momentum in Diverse Classroom Contexts	Teachers aged 41–50 and 51+	Demonstration lessons by younger peers, team teaching, pacing drills	Improved lesson continuity and pacing skills among older teachers
Day 2 AM	Understanding With-it-ness from Gender Perspectives	Male and Female Teachers	Empathy-building workshops, classroom simulation with reflection	Enhanced ability to anticipate and manage student behavior, especially among males
Day 2 PM	Instructional Practice Calibration by Qualification	Bachelor's, Master's, Doctorate holders	Comparative lesson planning, differentiated coaching, peer critique	Greater instructional cohesion regardless of academic background
Day 3 AM	Maintaining Instructional Flow and Transitions	Teachers without Master's degrees	Simulated classroom routines, transition games, microteaching	Improved transition handling and fewer instructional disruptions
Day 3 PM	Post-Training Evaluation and	All Participants	Lesson study, peer observation,	Ongoing support for teachers and

	Classroom-Based Reflection		coaching circles	data-informed adjustments to practice
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VI. Proposed Budget

Item No.	Particulars	Quantity	Unit Cost (₱)	Total (₱)
1	Meals and Snacks (AM snack, lunch, PM snack × 3 days)	90	250	22,500
2	Training Kits and Materials (folders, pens, notepads, modules)	30	200	6,000
3	Supplies and Printing (bond paper, ink, certificates)	—	—	3,000
4	Resource Speaker's Honorarium (2/day × 3 days)	6	2,000	12,000
5	Transportation (for speakers/staff)	3 days	1,500	4,500
6	Tokens of Appreciation for Speakers	6	500	3,000
7	Venue and Equipment Rental (projector, sound system)	3 days	2,000	6,000
8	Contingency (10% of total estimated cost)	—	—	5,725
	Total Estimated Budget			**₱62,725**

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to conducting the study, Ethics Clearance was sought from the PUP-UREC (University Research Ethics Center). Permission were sought from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent and from all school heads of the participating schools in Pasig. All participants were properly told about the goal of the research, and informed consent was obtained to ensure their voluntary participation. The respondents' confidentiality and identities were thoroughly maintained, and all data obtained was used purely for academic purposes.

Acknowledgments

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REFERENCES

- Aibinuomo, M. P. (2021). Effective Classroom Management: An overview of Critical Behaviour Expected of Teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Nigeria. *Rivers State University Journal of Education*, 24(2), 14-25.
<https://www.rsujoe.com.ng/index.php/joe/article/view/76/64>
- Ahmad, R., Hashmi, M. A., & Mukhtyar, M. (2022). Examining the Difference in Teachers' Instructional Behavior on the Basis of the Demographic Variables at the Secondary Level. *Global Educational Studies Review*, VII(I), 414–424.
[https://doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2022\(vii-i\).40](https://doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2022(vii-i).40)
<https://typeset.io/papers/examining-the-difference-in-teachers-instructional-behavior-1yzph4et>
- Akanbiemu, A. A., Ajibare, O. O., & Ogunwemimo, T. A. (2021). Library Use and Knowledge Sharing Amongst Undergraduates in Babcock University, Ilishan Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 0_1-33.

- https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Adetola-Akanbiemu/publication/351450488_Library_Use_And_Knowledge_Sharing_Amongst_Undergraduates_In_Babcock_University_Ilishan_Remo_Ogun_State_Nigeria/links/6396edee11e9f00cda3c0727/Library-Use-And-Knowledge-Sharing-Amongst-Undergraduates-In-Babcock-University-Ilishan-Remo-Ogun-State-Nigeria.pdf
- Barella, Y., Fergina, A., Mustami, M. K., Rahman, U., & Alajaili, H. M. A. (2024). Quantitative Methods in Scientific Research. *Jurnal Pendidikan Sosiologi Dan Humaniora*, 15(1), 281.
<https://doi.org/10.26418/j-psh.v15i1.71528>
- Basal, D. V. (2022). Instructional Competencies of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Teachers: Basis for a Competency-Based Module. *Instructional Competencies of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Teachers: Basis For A Competency-Based Module*, 96(1), 13-13.
[file:///C:/Users/324/Downloads/100951220222926%20\(3\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/324/Downloads/100951220222926%20(3).pdf)
- Benaning, J. A. (2023). Knowledge, Acceptance and Readiness to the K-12 Program Among Technical–Vocational Teachers. *American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation*, 2(2), 87-98.
<https://journals.e-palli.com/home/index.php/ajmri/article/view/1385>
- Berger, J.-L., Girardet, C., Vaudroz, C., & Crahay, M. (2018). Teaching Experience, Teachers' Beliefs, and Self-Reported Classroom Management Practices: A Coherent Network. *SAGE Open*, 8(1), 215824401775411.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244017754119>
<https://typeset.io/pdf/teaching-experience-teachers-beliefs-and-self-reported-1y0prmucy9.pdf>
- Calanog, M. C. B. (2021). Developing Technical Skills of Technology and Livelihood Education Secondary Teachers in the Province of Batangas. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, 4(12), 120-132.
<https://journal.ijresm.com/index.php/ijresm/article/view/1632>
- Coronel, H. S., & Ferrater-Gimena, J. A. (2017). Instructional Management Skills and Effectiveness of Physical Education Instructors in Higher Education Institutions in Cebu City, Philippines. *JPAIR Institutional Research*, 9(9), 69-84.
<https://www.philair.ph/index.php/irj/article/view/493>
- Cruz, A. G. (2023). Instructional Management Skills of Physical Education Teachers in Region IV-A: Basis for an Enhanced Instructional Program
- De La Torre, M. (2024). Classroom Management Skills of Public Elementary School Teachers. *GEO Academic Journal*, 5(1).
<https://doi.org/10.56738/issn29603986.geo2024.5.77>
<https://typeset.io/papers/classroom-management-skills-of-public-elementary-school-34d4v3arsnyy>
- Dela Cruz, V. T., II. (2021). Enhancing teaching Technology and Livelihood Education/Technical Vocation Education subject through bilingual medium of instruction. *International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR)*, 5(2), 141–145. <http://www.ijeais.org/ijamr>
<http://ijeais.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/2/IJAMR210218.pdf>
- Djalilov, J., Usmanov, I., Meliev, V., Alimov, S., & Sharopov, Z. (2023). MODERN

- METHODS OF TEACHING TECHNICAL SUBJECTS. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(4), 317-327.
<https://journals.uew.edu.gh/index.php/ghajet/article/view/218>
- Emmer, E. T., & Sabornie, E. J. (Eds.). (2015). *Handbook of classroom management*. New York: Routledge.
https://books.google.com.ph/books?hl=en&lr=&id=XUhsBAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&ots=qYa01o1A&sig=aVOcrNKk6HRlo3CcfDPzDndnuRc&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false
- Fontanilla, R., Fontanilla Jr, R., Galadi, D., & Nano, A. (2023). A Comparative Evaluation of the Technical Education System of the Philippines and England: An Integrative Literature Review. *Herculean Journal*, 1(1).
<https://herculeanjournal.com/index.php/main/article/view/2>
- Gunawan, I. I. (2017, August). The Application of Instructional Management Based Lesson Study and its Impact with Student Learning Achievement. In 2nd International Conference on Educational Management and Administration (CoEMA 2017) (pp. 412). Atlantis Press.
<https://www.atlantis-press.com/proceedings/coema-17/25882328>
- Hashmi, H., Nazim, F., & Batool, U. (2023). EFFECT OF INSTRUCTIONAL MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AT SECONDARY SCHOOL LEVEL IN QUETTA. *Pakistan Journal of Educational Research*, 6(2).
<https://www.pjer.org/index.php/pjer/article/view/805>
- Helsa, H., & Hendriati, A. (2017). Kemampuan manajemen kelas guru: penelitian tindakan di sekolah dasar dengan ses rendah. 16(2), 89–104.
<https://doi.org/10.14710/JP.16.2.89-104>
<https://typeset.io/pdf/kemampuan-manajemen-kelas-guru-penelitian-tindakan-di-14zrkd01nf.pdf>
- Kissi, E., Ahadzie, D. K., Debrah, C., & Adjei-Kumi, T. (2020). Underlying strategies for improving entrepreneurial skills development of technical and vocational students in developing countries: using Ghana as a case study. *Education+ Training*, 62(5), 599-614.
- Kizi, D. B. O., & Ugli, M. K. S. (2020). Roles of teachers in education of the 21st century. *Science and Education*, 1(3), 554-557.
<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/roles-of-teachers-in-education-of-the-21st-century>
- Koran, S., & Koran, E. (2018). Classroom management and school science labs: A review of literature on classroom management strategies. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 5(2), 64-72.
<https://ijsses.tiu.edu.iq/index.php/ijsses/article/view/618/601>
- Korpershoek, H., Harms, T., de Boer, H., van Kuijk, M., & Doolaard, S. (2016). A meta-analysis of the effects of classroom management strategies and classroom management programs on students' academic, behavioral, emotional, and motivational outcomes. *Review of educational research*, 86(3), 643-680.
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.3102/0034654315626799>
- Lau, K., & Gardner, D. (2019). Disciplinary variations in learning styles and preferences: Implications for the provision of academic English. *System*, 80, 257-268.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0346251X18300198>

- Na Ayutthaya, T. I., & Damrongpanit, S. (2022). A Meta-Analysis of Instructional Management Models Affecting Creative Thinking Development. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 11(4).
<https://www.eu-jer.com/a-meta-analysis-of-instructional-management-models-affecting-creative-thinking-development>
- Önen, E. (2022). Öğretmenlerin Sınıf Yönetimi Becerilerini Geliştirmelerine Etki Eden Sosyal ve Psikolojik Faktörler. *Sosyal Araştırmalar ve Davranış Bilimleri Dergisi*, 8(16), 380–392. <https://doi.org/10.52096/jsrbs.8.16.23>
<https://typeset.io/pdf/ogretmenlerin-sinif-yonetimi-becerilerini-gelistirmelerine-3to4namw.pdf>
- Pangan, S. B. (2022). Teaching Strategies of Technical-Vocational Teachers and Student Satisfaction. *Teaching Strategies of Technical-Vocational Teachers and Student Satisfaction*, 104(1), 24-24.
<https://ijrp.org/paper-detail/3559>
- Pranoto, Y. K., Utami, D. R. F., Latiana, L., & Ahmadi, F. (2021). Do Teachers' Experiences and Ages Contribute to Their Teaching Performance? <https://doi.org/10.46254/an11.20210629>
<https://www.ieomsociety.org/singapore2021/papers/629.pdf>
- Raganas, N. S., & Collado, L. S. (2016). Professional attributes: Implications to instructional management skills of teachers. *Annals of Studies in Science and Humanities*, 1(1), 84-94.
https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/80944062/74-libre.pdf?1645062018=&response-content-disposition=inline%3B+filename%3DProfessional_Attributes_Implications_to.pdf&Expires=1710593653&Signature=Wl2pqfwCxbX~vQNKz8iÖMY9f9BTZ1141A6tMrM11F~8ffaDhztOaMqYbLATjIgu~UXarmh2BCPEUycBYyQofnC~BgO909Q~o uiyCSovKpVFrzNiXvXjzgtxJTtrlmt2h8IRt-65tJc-z7~~3ZeAVX7Inb3auZD-XNQDlf5fn4gokcThtZfh91cj1dll8QNJGDlrmKXvf4SOVlpC6L-6j2ePeYyJBbOti9J5eMYECUqAC0wij2e~JgEfezncA9AJngl9-WaU0ZOHO8DNyaybz5sIblwXGWhdluw7T3~eGyrtX94~FEUIGtaQWbKiSj0pWIKkFxxO5dg9tdrwA5Se9A__&Key-Pair-Id=APKAJLOHF5GGSLRBV4ZA
- Raganas, N. S., & Collado, L. S. (2016). Professional Attributes: Implications to Instructional Management Skills of Teachers. 1(1), 84–94.
<http://journal.carsu.edu.ph/index.php/assh/article/download/63/74>
<https://typeset.io/pdf/professional-attributes-implications-to-instructional-3aox480lc1.pdf>
- Rana, H. P. (2022). INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES OF TECHNOLOGY LIVELIHOOD AND EDUCATION TEACHERS TO THE STUDENTS'SATISFACTION AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE, 102(1), 14-14.
<https://ijrp.org/paper-detail/3283>
- Supriyono, S. (2016). INSTRUCTIONAL MANAGEMENT OF ESP FOR AGROTECHNOLOGY AND AGRIBUSINESS STUDIES: AN EXPERIENTIAL REFLECTIVE PRACTICE. *IJOTL-TL: Indonesian Journal of Language Teaching and Linguistics*, 1(2), 97-110.
<https://ijotl-tl.soloclcs.org/index.php/ijotl/article/view/88>

- Tamayo, S. B. (2023). Status of Technical-Vocational and Technology and Livelihood Education Instruction in CSU: Input for A Training Program. *AIDE Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 6, 46-64.
- Tan, M. C. (2021). Technology and livelihood education (TLE) instruction in the secondary schools in northern Samar division, eastern Philippines. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*, 15(2), 75-84.
<https://journalajarr.com/index.php/AJARR/article/view/308>
- UNESCO. (2016). Strategy for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) (2016-2021).. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000245239>
http://unevoc.ru/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/Strategy_2016-2021_eng-1.pdf
- Ugurlu, C. T., Usta, G., & Köybaşı, F. (2019). An Investigation of Teachers' Classroom Management Skills in terms of Gender Variability: A Meta-Analysis Study. *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 11(1).
<https://doi.org/10.15345/IOJES.2019.01.006>
<https://typeset.io/papers/an-investigation-of-teachers-classroom-management-skills-in-24340whuiq>